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Analysis Of Communication Skills Problems Of Some Lecturers In Shehu Shagari College Of Education, Sokoto

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ABSTRACT

English language is one of the global languages and spoken in many countries of the world. It is also one of the languages used by the United Nations. Like any language, English has its rules and pattern of usage which help to pass information or knowledge to audience or learners appropriately. The way the language is used by the speaker can affect the audience or the learner positively or negatively. That is to say when a lecturer presents his lectures and used the appropriate language, it will help to make the lesson comprehensive and the desired change in behaviour will occur. Therefore, clear and accurate understanding of the language of communication by the lecturer is very imperative for any meaningful learning to take place. English language is the official language in Nigeria and many subjects in tertiary institutions in the country use it as means of communication in lectures and other academic gatherings. It is based on this belief that this research investigated the communication skills competencies of some lecturers in English language in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto while conducting their lessons. The research sampled randomly 22 lecturers and their lecture presentations were recorded without them knowing. The research found out that there were 10 main errors patterning to use of English Language in the presentations of the sampled lecturers and 368 total errors of occurrences. Some of these errors include: **Errors in sentence patterns/ structure words(27.2%)** Inappropriate use of prepositions (3.0%), Concord/Agreement or problems of subject and verb (15.4.%, errors in sounds pattern (17.9%), errors in words pattern and Code Switching /Direct Method (13.3%) among others. The research recommended that Teachers or lecturers with appropriate communication skills and competences should be employed, there should be mentorship in the College so that the newly employed lecturers can be groomed by the older and well experienced ones, Lecturers should be trained from time to time on communication skills and improvement of language, Quality Assurance Unit of the College should try to identify the areas of problems of lecturers whether relating to communication or delivery of content or knowledge of the subject matter as a whole, or lack of adequate teaching pedagogy and other shortcomings that will affect proper teaching and learning in the College.

Keywords: communication, English language, teaching, learning, sentence patterns

INTRODUCTION

Language and communication are inseparable. This is because communication contains messages for recipients but the messages cannot be understood clearly except through language. This language must be

clearly understood by the communicator as well as the recipients of the message. This is very important in learning institutions whose main objective is to communicate various messages or knowledge to learners. Understanding the language of communication is therefore very imperative. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, English Language is the main medium of communication and this means that understanding the language by the teacher as well as the student is of paramount importance if proper learning is to take place.

Statement of the Problem

Evidence abounds from research or otherwise that about three decades ago there has been a dwindling down trend of the performance of students leading to mass failures mainly due to their inability to put down on paper concepts, ideas, definitions of what they have learnt or grasped in appropriate English on paper. Why do we most often blame the students? Can they give what they don't have? Is it not then a situation of garbage in garbage out? With the introduction of its compulsory Basic Education in the country, there was a massive increase in the enrolment of pupils and definitely a corresponding increase in the employment of teachers qualified or otherwise. This phenomenon continued to affect the schools, institutions of learning until it becomes evident to us that the communication English of a good number of staff is a serious cause for concern that can be heard, discuss openly in formal and informal gatherings. In SSCO, Sokoto, it becomes even more worrisome when (some of the good students) come out openly to criticise some teachers. It becomes more worrisome when we hear some students saying they attend some lectures not because they want to but because they want to copy some of the numerous communication errors some lecturers commit while delivering their lectures so that they will have a good laugh at the end.

Objectives of the Study

The broad aim and objectives of this research was to investigate the communicative skills competence of some lecturers in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto in English language while delivering their lessons and the effects on teaching and learning. But the specific objectives of the study were to :

1. Identify the communication skill competences in English Language of some lecturers in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto
2. Identify use of unusual expressions, constructions, ungrammatical expressions, misuse of words, wrong pronunciations etc in the presentation of lessons
3. Analyze the recorded lecture presentation of some lecturers in the College using English language communication skills rules.
4. Find ways that will help lecturers in the College to improve their communication skills in their lessons in English

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted different approaches or multifarious methods as follows:

Research Design

The researchers mapped out different language rules like grammar, use of verbs and tenses etc to assess the lecturers practically during the lesson presentations

Population of the Study

The total number of the lecturers in the College is about 650 but only 22 lecturers were randomly sampled due to many factors instead of the 50 earlier planned to be sampled.

Instrument for Data Collection/Materials

This study used various modern devices to record the lessons of 22 lecturers across the 7 schools of the College. Spy pen recorders were initially used to record presentation of lecturers while they were delivering their lecture but not aware of the recording. However, the use of the spy pen recorders was discontinued because of their technicalities to use. The researchers therefore resorted to recording with phones. This was done at different times and venues while randomly sampled lecturers were making their lecture presentations.

Method of Data Collection

- a) The researchers secured consent permit from the College Management prior to commencement of data collection. This consent note was circulated to the College community.
- b) Recording of lectures presented by the randomly selected lecturers was done through Class Representatives who were used as research assistants. The lecture presentations of 22 lecturers were recorded while their lectures were progressing and without them knowing.
- c) After the recording period, the researchers collated the various recorded lessons of the lecturers and played them severally trying to identify the communication skills errors or otherwise. During this process it was discovered that 12 out of the 22 recorded presentation were faulty. The recordings were poor and can be understood clearly. Therefore, the researchers were compelled to restrict themselves to only 10.
- d) Analyzing these lessons based on the rules of English language to ascertain the degree of compliances with the rules of Communicative skills by the lecturers and show the extent at which the contents of these lessons were accurately presented to the learners was very tedious. The analysis was based on the rules of English Language. Many aspects of English Language were used to analyze the presentations. Among these rules used were the use of verbs and subjects, pronouns, nouns, sentence structures, patterns among others.

DATA PRESENTATION

Therefore, in the process of analyzing the presentations in order to find out their compliances with laid down rules and regulations of English communication, the following 10 aspects of language were used as yardsticks as show in table 1 below:

Table 1: Aspects of Communication Skills in English Used as Yardstick to Analyze Lecture Presentations of Lecturers in SSCO, Sokoto

S/No	Aspects of English Language
1.	Errors in sentence patterns/ structure words
2.	None use of structural signals (articles etc) or inappropriate use of them
3.	Errors in words pattern
4.	Incomplete statements
5.	Abuse of hesitation fillers
6.	Errors in sounds pattern
7.	Abuse of the use of the Direct Method/Code-switching
8.	Concord/Agreement
9.	Redundancy/ verbosity/ use of unnecessary words
10.	Inappropriate use of pre-positions

Source : Field Work 2024

Table 1 above shows the major aspects of errors that were observed and used to analyze the presentations of the sampled lecturers.

Table 2 showing the Analysis of the Recorded Lecture Presentation of Some Lecturers in Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto

S/No	Error Type	R/pr esen tatio n 1	R/pre senta tion 2	R/pre senta tion 3	R/pres entatio n 4	R/pre senta tion 5	R/pre senta tion 6	R/pr esen tatio n 7	R/pre senta tion 8	R/pre senta tion 9	R/pres entatio n 10	Total
1	Errors in sentence patterns/ structure words	14	17	10	7	7	6	22	4	6	7	100
2	None use of structural signals (articles etc) or inappropriate use of them	2	8	4	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	24
3	Errors in words pattern	5	16	4	6	25	0	8	0	0	2	66
4	Incomplete statements	2	8	2	2	7	1	12	0	0	0	34
5	Abuse of hesitation fillers	4	6	2	5	5	0	3	0	0	0	25
6	Errors in sounds pattern	1	1	7	0	0	3	4	0	2	2	20
7	Abuse of the use of the Direct Method/Code-switching	3	2	7	0	22	8	0	5	2	0	49
8	Concord/Agreement	0	2	0	0	0	1	11	0	0	1	15
9	Redundancy/ verbosity/ use of unnecessary words	2	2	0	2	2	1	14	0	1	0	24
10	Inappropriate use of prepositions	1	1	0	2	0	0	6	0	1	0	11
		34	63	36	24	68	20	90	9	12	12	368
	Total	368										

Source: Field Work Survey, 2024

From table 2 above, the analysis of the number of errors in the 10 language aspects per each presentation. It shows that the total language communication errors found out by the analysis of the presentations of the 10 lecturers was 368. Out of this number, **Errors in sentence patterns/ structure words** has the highest with 100 occurrences across the presenters. This represents (27.2%). It is followed by **Errors in words pattern** which has 66 occurrences across the presentations, representing 17.9%. This is followed by **Abuse of the use of the Direct Method/Code-switching** with 49 occurrences, representing 13.3%. **Incomplete statements** is the next with 34 occurrences, representing 9.2%. **Abuse of hesitation fillers**

has 25 occurrences representing 6.8%. **None use of structural signals (articles etc) or inappropriate use of them** and **Redundancy/ verbosity/ use of unnecessary words** have 24 occurrences each, presenting 6.5% each. The aspects with the lowest occurrences are respectively **Errors in sounds pattern. Concord/Agreement** and **Inappropriate use of prepositions**. Their occurrences were respectively 20 (5.4%), 15 (4.1%) and 11 (3.0%).

Similarly, from the same table 2 , it can be seen that the Recorded Presentation with the highest rate of errors is **Recorded Presentation number 7** who has a total of 90 errors, representing 24.5%. This is followed by **Recorded Presentation Number 5** with a total of 68 errors, representing 18.5%. Then, **Recorded presentation Number 2**, who has a total of 63 errors, representing 17.1% The **Recorded Presentation Number 3** followed with a total errors of 36, representing 9.8%. 34 is the total errors of **Recorded Presentation Number 1** and this represents 9.2%. This number is followed by **Recorded Presentation** with a total of 24, representing 6.5%. it is followed by **Recorded Presentation Number 6** with a total of 20 errors, representing 5.4%. The Recorded Presentation with the lowest errors are 9 (2,5%)and 12 (3.3%) and respectively Recorded Presentation Numbers 8, 9 and 10.

Discussions on the Identified 10 Aspects of Language Communication

As pointed out above that the researchers in the process of analyzing the recorded lecture presentations, were able to identify 10 English language communication issues and therefore, they briefly discussed below.

Patterns in English

Patterning in English refers to the use and arrangement of words in an appropriate order or position so that we can predict more or less what is going to happen. For example look at these sentences:

A: Give me a cup of water

B. Me cup of water a give

Though in the two sentence, the same words are used to construct the sentences, the arrangement of the positioning of the words in A makes sense while that of B does not.

Errors in Sentence Patterns/ Words Structure

/Sentence pattern refers to the appropriate ways in which sentences are put together to make sense. in English our sentences usually operate using patterns which include subject, verb and object. Sentence pattern is the order and ype of phrases and clauses in sentences. There are four types of sentence patterns which include simple sentence, compound sentence, complex sentence and compound complex sentence. It is noteworthy to understand that sentences in English depends on word order to make sense and also that a sentence is made up of content words (the Bricks) and structure words *the Cenment). There are 5 major sentence patterns in English. They are:

i. Noun plus verb eg.

The dog barked.

ii. Noun plus verb plus noun. Eg,

Kande bought a shirt

iii. Noun plus (verb to be) plus noun

Eg. This is an egg.

iv. Noun plus verb to be plus adjective

Eg. Her car is red

v. Noun plus verb to be plus adverb

Eg. The bottle is under the chair

Ironically, in the research, the bottle is under the chair, we discovered that this aspect of English Language was not applied knowingly or unknowingly by the sampled lecturers. That's why in the table above, the errors that occurred in this regards was 100, representing (27.2%). The implication of this is that it makes the presentation unclear or ambiguous to the learners. Consequently poor comprehension which leads to poor or low performance

Code Switching /Direct Method

Direct method is the use of the mother tongue instead of the official language in teaching in the classroom. Code switching on the hand is the phenomenon common among bilingual speech communities, in which speakers switch from one language to another within the same conversation (McGregor, 2009). By making choices among the available languages within the process of the lectures some lecturers were observed to code switch from the national language (English) to vernacular (Hausa) which is the predominant spoken language in Sokoto State. Therefore, failing to vary their teaching within a single discuss (English Language) with either the motive of making their lessons understood by the students they code switch in a bit to achieve the communicative purpose or they code switch because they lack the communicative skills in the official language to impart the required knowledge.

The implications of this are that learners will not be encouraged to learn the communication skills in English; they will not be able to communicate the ideas taught to them adequately during examinations because the questions required their to respond in English language and finally, the method will affect learners that do not understand the vernacular, here Hausa.

None use of structural signals (articles etc) or inappropriate use of them

Structural signals refer to words that help to bring out the intended meaning in a sentence from a speaker. This includes words like a, an, the, they, it, we, he, she, etc. these words help to bring out the meanings in a sentence and show where the speaker is making reference. 'Let alone, the words do not have much meaning in themselves but serve as cement which binds sentences together'. For instance, the sentence "Strike ends quickly". This sentence could be interpreted differently. It could mean the strike of some workers has ended quickly. It could also mean, you must strike the ends of these objects quickly. There is no way of telling which of these two meanings is intended. But if we put in the word "the" however, we can see at once what it means. We can have:

The strike ends quickly or

Strike the ends quickly

And there is no question about the meaning.

In our recorded lecture presentation by sampled lecturers, few examples can be given as follows:

- a. So that prevent external attack. In this sentence, the lecturer failed to add the pronoun "They" rendered the sentence incomplete or meaningless. The sentence is supposed to read: So that they can prevent external attack.
- b. Is because they think instead..... In this sentence also, the lecturer fails to include the word "It" and this has rendered the meaning of the sentence incomplete or ambiguous.
- c. Draws a columns 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6... Here the lecturer added the article "a" before the plural word columns. The article 'a' is not supposed to be there. Though we can infer meaning from the sentence, it looks awkward.

Errors in words pattern

This is another communication errors detected from the presentations of the sampled lecturers. Words pattern refers to the sequence of consonants and vowels in a word which can range from basic to more complex. The arrangement of letters within words or the way words are placed in a sentence is another meaning of word pattern. Again in the area of word structure we found that there is a regular pattern. Normally an 's' on the end of a noun means that the noun is in the plural. If the that 'S' in on the end of the verb, it means that it is in the present tense, and subject is in the third person. Similarly, the suffix--- 'ed' shows that the verb is in the past tense. Though there are exceptions to this rule, but this is in most cases the normal pattern.

Examples of such errors discovered include:

- a. How many times students scored 1, 2., 3, 4, 5, 6 In this sentence, the teacher asked a question instead of using the verb score 'd' was added to the base word making it a past tense which is wrong or an error.

- b. How many times it appears instead of..... In this sentence, the pronoun was wrongly used instead of the verb to be does. The question is supposed to read thus: "How many times does it appear....."
- c. Why we said..... Here the past tense of the verb was wrongly used by the lecturer instead of saying "Why we say..."
- d. So that Kuwait now seek for interaction.... The verb seek was wrongly used instead of the past tense of the verb sought.

Incomplete statements

Incomplete statement refers to sentences that are stopped half way without being complete thereby making the meaning of what the lecturer wants to convey to the learners ambiguous or leaving them in state of confusion or uncertainty.. in the recorded lecture presentations of the sampled lecturers, we have many of this examples. Some are as follows:

- a. To hear incidences of banditry attacks, the same Nigerians who works hard to fight against issues every day you hear incidences of banditry attacks here and there, every you hear the something you see people are soliciting for prayers for divine intervention and..... against these banditry attacks the same Nigerians who fought for slavery the same Nigerians who worked hard to fight against issues of kidnapping, human trafficking, yet the same Nigerians are also banditry and kidnapping people.....
The reader is left to make his or her own deduction on this.
- b. The tenth scores can be arranged in descending order for meaningful How many students scores 21, 23, 24, 46, 53..... Here the lecturer has not completed the sentences.

Abuse of hesitation fillers

By hesitation fillers we refer to exclamations like 'eem', 'mhm', 'ahm', 'am', 'ehm' etc. Hesitation is the act of pausing while communicating. It happens mostly when the vocabulary to express ideas is lacking. Many examples were recorded in the. Course of this research and few examples are shown below.

- a. When I was an undergraduate..... I have Am.. ehm security men ... this man start doing his work.... This sentence conveys nothing.
- b. Eh is that whatyou have to use some document, some written materials in your research writing.
- c. I work against it next time ehm mm.
No meaning is derivable from this sentence or statement.

Errors in sounds pattern

English has 44 sounds that fall into the following categories: Consonants, Diagraphs, Diphthongs, Vowels and r-controlled vowels. A diagraph is a sound that generates from a combination of two letters. Example ph, gh and ey. In the area of English sounds, we find various examples of this. For instance, a/p/ and an /n/ will come together at the end of a word, eg 'happen', but never at the beginning (in words like pneumonia, the 'P' is silent). On the other hand, the combination /sp/ comes at the end of a word (wasp) and also at the beginning (spell). Similarly, we have 'hurdle', and 'glue', but, though we have 'hurdle', there is no word beginning with /dl/ in English. But in the course of this research we found out that in pronunciation anything /th/ majority of the lecturers have glaring native tongue influence in their sound patterns and this have some bearings on the delivery of the lectures or ideas to the learners.

Redundancy/ verbosity/ use of unnecessary words

Redundancy/use of unnecessary words or verbosity means the use of words that are not required or are not necessary in a sentence or statement. This occurs due to lack of language or vocabulary to express intended ideas to learners or listeners. verbosity on other hand means use of too many words to explain a

concept instead of being direct or straight forward in providing the required explanation or meaning. This aspect of language error was observed in this research. For example:

One of the reasons **why complexity of modern states**, when we say **complexity of modern state**, is today the powerful you are when we are discussing with, you see in life not only when we are discussing with whole and are.... **States or nations in the world we are just a kind of are inter-connections. When we say inter-connections states cannot are no nations in the world over** an island of itself. It is just like **an individuals** you cannot survive or when you interact only yourself. **Is it possible for somebody to leads his life without interaction without other members of his family or society?** Which is not possible. **Like states most interact with one another for certain purposes.** That is why we said the reasons why some countries have to come together and interact. That interaction is what we called international political system. I you with me?

Here the lecturer was trying to explain to the students about natio~~s~~/states and the need to interact with one another.

Concord/Agreement

Concord is the grammatical agreement between the subject and the verb in a sentence (<https://unacademic.com>kerala-psc>). It is also known as subject-verb agreement. For example, the verb must be plural if the subject is plural and vice visa. In our investigation we found elements of non-compliance with this aspect of English language among the sampled lecturers. Few instances are shown below:

- a. No nations in the world over is an island of itself.
In this sentence, the subject nations does not concord with the verb is. This is because nations is in plural form while is is in singular form .
- b. One of the reasons why complexity of modern state.....
In this sentence too the presenter has failed to concord with subject-verb aspect of English language when he states that “one of the reasons why complexity of modern states”. He should stated that “one of the reasons is complexity of modern state.”
- c. Is it possible for somebody to leads his life without interaction?
Here the lack of concord is the misuse of the verb lead with addition of ‘s’ which in the third person singular form.
- d. Any country that has nuclear energy in abundance many countries will like to interacts with that particular country.
In this sentence the subject many countries does not agree with the verb interacts which is in the third person singular.

Inappropriate use of Prepositions

A pre-position is a word or group of words that connects nouns, pronouns or phrases to other words in a sentence. Prepositions can show direction, place, location, spatial relationship or introduce an object in a sentence (Oxford online Dictionary).

Some of the inappropriate use of pre-positions observed in the research include:

- a. Wear your Hijab that you know is comfortable for you.
In this sentence the error is the use of wrong pre-position ‘for’ instead of ‘to’.
- b. I sent two people, one got a nylon with moisture on it. They all bring what I have ask them to bring.
In this sentence, the clause ‘They all bring’ supposed to be “both brought what I have asked them to bring’.
- c. You are writing a research..... to the performance of the student.
The sentence should read as “You are writing a research about the performance of the student””. Here the lecturer used the wrong preposition ‘to’ instead of about.

CONCLUSION

To conclude this article, it is important to note that English is important to be learnt irrespective of whether one is an English student or not. The rules governing the usage of the language must be learnt and clearly understood. This is paramount because it is the medium of communication. We have seen from the presentations of some of the lecturers that what they wanted to communicate to the students were not stated clearly and this affects learning. This consequently will affect the quality of the students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on what was presented above, we would like to proffer the following recommendations

1. English Language is the main medium of teaching in Nigeria and the College in particular, therefore, teachers or lecturers should be made to learn appropriate communication skills and competences that will help them in their assignments
2. During recruitments for lecturers, there should be thorough screening based not only on paper qualifications but also on the ability to communicate the subject matter clearly to the learners
3. There should be mentorship in the College so that the newly employed lecturers can be groomed by the older and well experienced lecturers.
4. Lecturers should be trained from time to time on communication skills and improvement of language.
5. Quality Assurance Unit of the College should identify lecturers with English Language communication skills problems and assist in addressing them by liaising with relevant stakeholders.

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